

COMPARATIVE EVALUATION OF STATISTICAL METHODS FOR MAPPING DEBRIS FLOW SUSCEPTIBILITY IN HIMALAYAS, INDIA

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ABSTRACT

Comparing maps from different statistical models or approaches is important for geo-environmental uses. This paper uses various models to compare debris flow susceptibility maps of the same area. The frequency of debris flow in hilly regions requires future developmental planning and study. A crucial step in studying debris flow is weighing the factors causing it. This paper compares different weighting procedures for debris flow susceptibility mapping through map evaluation. The evaluation has been done through frequency ratio and Shannon entropy statistical models. According to the difference image analysis, there is a complete matching (i.e., no difference) of roughly 86.61% of the total pixels between the two debris flow susceptibility maps. It is possible to interchange frequency ratio and Shannon entropy models based on their similar image analysis values.

KEYWORDS

Debris flow susceptibility zonation; Comparative evaluation; Difference image analysis

1. INTRODUCTION

Global maps and spatial data have increased during the last five years due to the deployment of satellite sensors and GIS technologies. Maps can use multiple data structures, such as raster or vector, and illustrate various themes, such as slope, vegetation cover, lithology, and rainfall. Different pre-processing methods, assumptions, conceptual models, algorithms, or even just temporal circumstances might cause variances in maps depicting the same theme property of the same region (such as vegetation density or landslide susceptibility). Researchers have become increasingly interested in this over time (see, for example, Monsrud and Leemans, 1992; Pontius et al., 2004) as it necessitates the development of proper map comparison methodologies. GIS-based data analysis processes provide methods for integrating various spatial data types (Gupta, 2003). Essential environmental studies have demonstrated the significant benefits that sophisticated GIS computational tools provide in handling multiple geodata sets. These studies don't, however, compare maps produced by GIS at the geographical level. The comparative evaluation of spatial maps using different image analysis is the main topic of this paper. The last several years have seen a lot of interest in studies on debris flow and debris flow susceptibility mapping. A debris flow susceptibility mapping classifies regions or zones according to the degree of current or anticipated debris flow dangers. It typically depicts the spatial distribution of various debris flow susceptibility regions, such as those with very high (VHS), high (HS), moderate (MS), low (LS), and very low (VLS) susceptibility zones, which are represented on an ordinal scale. In the literature, examples of numerous such maps created using GIS-based methods and utilizing various weight assignment algorithms have been published (Kanungo et al., 2006). Additionally, from remote sensing data, thematic data layers referring to several causal elements impacting the occurrence of debris flows have been created, for which raster-based processing in a GIS framework was the obvious choice. In this study, Shannon entropy- and frequency-based debris flow raster maps have been compared and evaluated. This comparison will help understand how the same causal elements might have different effects on the incidence of debris flows in a test region in the Uttarakhand Himalayas.

2. STUDY AREA

The Indian state of Uttarakhand, originally known as Uttaranchal, is situated in the northwest of the nation, and Nepal has a common international border to the east and north, respectively. 53,483 km² in size, Uttarakhand is located between 28°43' and 31°27' N latitude and 77°34' and 81°02' E longitude. The geography of Uttarakhand is extremely diverse, with snow-capped peaks, glaciers, steep canyons, roaring streams, stunning lakes, and a few isolated areas of dusty plains in the south. Uttarakhand is home to some of the world's tallest mountains. Especially noteworthy among them is Nanda Devi, India's second-highest summit. Several physiographic zones may be identified in Uttarakhand, all of which run parallel to one another from northwest to southeast [SFR, 2009]. With elevations spanning generally between 3,000 and 7,600 metres, the northern zone, sometimes referred to as the Himadri, is home to portions of the Great Himalaya and the Zaskar Mountain ranges. This zone contains the majority of the high peaks. The Lesser Himalayas, often referred to as the Himachal and located south and next to the Great Himalayas, with an elevation range of around 2,000 to 3,000 metres. Nag Tibba and Mussoorie are the two linear ranges in the zone. The Siwalik Range extends in the direction of the Himachal to the south. The Kumaun Himalayas generally refer to the entire region, including the Himadri, Himachal, and Siwalik. The Bhabar, a slender gravel and alluvial plain, and the Tarai, a marshy region, are located to the southeast and southwest, respectively, of the southernmost edge of the Siwalik Range. The united Siwalik-Bhabar-Tarai region has an elevation range of 300 to 3,000 metres. Flat-floored depressions, locally referred to as duns, such as the Dehra Dun, can be found south of the Siwalik.

Fig. 1. Location of the study area

3. METHODOLOGY FOR DEBRIS FLOW SUSCEPTIBILITY ZONATION (DFSZ) MODELLING

Twelve factors identified as impacting the debris flows in the study area were considered for this purpose. In the methodology flow chart, all the specific steps and phases of this investigation are listed (Fig. 2). The current study's application of statistical approaches, which are data-driven methods, is

predicated on the idea that debris flow events from the past and present are crucial for predicting future debris flows in certain hilly terrain (Kanungo et al. 2006). Instead of defining weights on a crisp scale as in the traditional expert opinion-based approach, statistical techniques establish the weights on a continuous scale through statistical training, delivering more accurate values in an objective manner. This helps to remove subjectivity and bias in weight assignment. (Kanungo et al. 2020).

3.1 Creating a database and identifying characteristics that cause debris flows.

In this section, a database is being created to identify the causes of debris flows. The factors that trigger debris flows can vary from place to place, and there is no single method for creating maps that predict where debris flows might occur. The selection of factors to consider is based on field observations, existing literature, and expert knowledge.

For instance, in some locations, factors like geology, elevation, slope, aspect, and curvature play a crucial role in debris flow prediction, while in others, proximity to rivers, drainage density, and specific terrain indexes are more relevant. Additionally, factors such as rock type, distance from roads, vegetation, and even rainfall or earthquake activity may be considered, depending on the availability of data and the specific study area.

In this research study, twelve criteria were considered: rainfall, geology, elevation, slope, aspect, curvature, lithology, distance to roads, distance to faults/lineaments, distance to rivers, topographic wetness index, and stream power index. Most of these criteria are derived from digital elevation models (DEM). The necessary data for this research were collected from various sources, as listed in Table 1, to determine the factors influencing debris flows in the study region.

Table 1: Debris flow causative factors data and their sources

<u>DATA</u>	<u>DATA SOURCE</u>
Digital Elevation Model	Open Topography: SRTM GLI Global, Resolution: 30m.
Lithology, Roads, Lineament, Rivers, Debris flow Points	Bhukosh Portal, Geological Survey of India.
India Districts Shapefile	Advances in Geographical Research
Rainfall Data from 2011 to 2020	Climatic Research Unit (CRU)
Geology	U.S. Geological Survey Open-File Report 97-470C

3.3 Adopted DFSZ models.

3.3.1 Frequency ratio (FR) model

Among bivariate statistical approaches, frequency analysis is the most extensively employed Angillieri (2020). The spatial distribution of prior debris flow in the area, as well as the association between these key causative factor groups, are utilised in this method (Achour 2018; Qin 2019 & Wu 2019). FR was firstly calculated for each class of each factor using Microsoft Excel and then, the corresponding relative frequencies along with the prediction rate for each factor was computed. Individual factor classes were then reclassified by changing their existing values by the relative frequency (RF) values. Then, individual prediction rates (PR) will be multiplied with the reclassified factor classes through the “Raster Calculator” tool in ArcMap through which, the debris flow susceptibility map for the study area will be generated. The FR as well as RF values for each class of each causative factor were computed using Eq. (1) and Eq. (2).

$$FR = \frac{\%Landslide\ Pixels}{\%Class\ Pixels} \quad (1)$$

$$RF = \frac{FR}{\text{Total sum of Frequency Ratios for that causative factor}} \quad (2)$$

Then, the prediction rate (PR) for all the twelve debris flow causative factors (DFCF) can be calculated in excel as:

$$PR \text{ for a DFCF} = \frac{(RF_{\max} - RF_{\min})}{(RF_{\max} - RF_{\min})_{\min}} \quad (3)$$

Therefore, twelve values of PR for each corresponding debris flow causative factor will be obtained. After the reclassification of each factor class in GIS after replacing their existing values with their respective relative frequencies, the debris flow susceptibility Zonation map for the area can be generated through the raster calculator in GIS by using following equation 6.

$$DFSZ = \sum(PR \text{ for a DFCF}) * (\text{Corresponding DFCF}) \quad (4)$$

3.3.2 Shannon Entropy (SE):

Entropy shows randomness or disorder ness in a continuous probability distribution data set. Basically, it is used to represent the instability or uncertainty in a given data set in natural phenomena (Shannon, 1948). In this method, individual weights for each debris flow causative factor are calculated and those calculated weights will be multiplied with each causative factor in GIS through the raster calculator tool. Numerically, it can be easily visualized as an extension of the FR method because the weight calculation for each factor is based on RF values calculated for the FR method. For the calculation of weights for each debris flow causative factor, the following equations (5) and (6) are used:

$$E = -K \sum RF * \ln(RF) \quad (5)$$

$$K = \frac{1}{\ln(M)}, E = \text{Entropy Value} \quad (6)$$

Where M= number of classes in each landslide causative factor

Now, the individual weight for each factor can be calculated through the following equation (9):

$$W_i = \frac{1-E}{\sum(1-E)} \quad (7)$$

Now, the Debris Flow Susceptibility Zonation Map for the taken study area can be computed by multiplying each debris flow causative factor with their corresponding calculated weights through the Shannon Entropy technique as shown in the following equation (8):

$$DFSZ = \sum(\text{Individual Weight for each DFCF}) * (\text{Corresponding DFCF}) \quad (8)$$

4. Results and Discussion

4.1 Implementation of Debris Flow Susceptibility Model

The maps depicting the zones of debris flow susceptibility were created using equations (4) and (8) by the incorporation of the raster calculator tool after reclassifying each debris flow causative factor. The debris flows susceptibility maps prepared after the application of the FR and SE models were classified into five susceptibility classes (Very Low, Low, Moderate, High, and Very High) as shown in figures 3 and 4.

Fig 3. Debris Flow Susceptibility Map using Frequency Ratio

Fig 4. Debris Flow Susceptibility Map using Shannon Entropy

The debris flow susceptibility map generated by the frequency ratio model shows that out of the total taken study area, 0.12%, 19.36%, 18.49%, 23.28%, and 38.73% area lie in the zone of very low, low, moderate, high and very high debris flow susceptibility respectively. However, the debris flow susceptibility map generated by the incorporation of the Shannon Entropy model depicts that 0.23%, 22.15%, 13.66%, 32.95%, and 31.02 area fall in the zone of very low, low, moderate, high, and very high debris flow susceptibility respectively.

4.3.2 Difference Image Analysis

Based on the DFSZ mapping procedure used, difference image analysis illustrates how pixels shift from one debris flow susceptibility zone to another. The VL, L, M, H, and VH zones of both DFSZ maps have been given the corresponding attributes 1, 2, 3, 4, and 5. By subtracting the pixel attributes of one DFSM map from the other, difference images are produced. As a result, a difference image can only have five different classes: four-zone differences, three-zone differences, two-zone differences, one-zone differences, and no differences. In the difference image, the no difference class would be represented by exactly matching pixels in the two DFSZ maps. With regard to pixel matching/mismatching in various debris flow susceptibility zones, the difference image thus shows the spatial consistency of two DFSZ maps DFSZ maps DFSZ_FR and DFSZ_SE have been combined for the current analysis's comparative evaluation. The outcomes of the difference image analysis are shown in Table 2. Fig. 5 displays the difference image of the DFSZ_FR and DFSZ_SE maps that was created by subtracting one from the other in GIS, and Table 2 contains the data that was retrieved from the difference image. According to the difference image analysis, there is a complete matching (i.e., no difference) of roughly 86.61% of the total pixels between the two DFSZ maps (Table 2; Fig. 6). Additionally, there are no pixels with a three-zone or four-zone difference, and only 11.07 percent and 2.32 percent of all pixels had one-zone or two-zone variances, respectively.

Fig.5 Difference images of DFSZ maps: a DFSZ_FR–DFSZ_SE

Table 2 Shows the outcomes of different image analyses of DFSZ maps.

Difference Image	No difference		One-zone difference		Two-zone difference		Three-zone difference		Four-zone difference	
	Number of pixels	Area (%)	Number of pixels	Area (%)	Number of pixels	Area (%)	Number of pixels	Area (%)	Number of pixels	Area (%)
DFSZ_FR-DFSZ_SE	50109743	86.61	6407718	11.07	1342426	2.32	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

Fig.6 Frequency distribution of pixels in difference image classes.

5 Conclusion

Given the increase in the number and incidence of debris flows in India's hilly regions as a result of a changing climate regime, an innovative attempt at DFSZ mapping has been made in the current study. The practical use of statistical models is one of the innovative characteristics of this research on GIS-based DFSZ mapping. A DFSZ map comparison was assessed using difference images. According to the difference image analysis, there is a complete matching (i.e., no difference) of roughly 86.61% of the total pixels between the two debris flow susceptibility maps. It is possible to interchange frequency ratio and Shannon entropy models based on their similar image analysis values. In order to manage and mitigate disasters, it may be advantageous to incorporate recognised influencing factors into the Geographic information system using either the FR or SE model.

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Ankit Kumar is a dedicated Ph.D. scholar at Delhi Technological University, focusing his research on the critical study of debris flow and landslides. With a passion for understanding natural phenomena, Ankit's work delves into the complexities of these geological events, aiming to contribute valuable insights to the field of geoscience and hazard mitigation.

